

TEACHING ENGLISH PRECEDENT PHENOMENA AT LINGUISTIC UNIVERSITY

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Abstract. *This article explores the importance of teaching English precedent phenomena in linguistic universities. The main focus is on describing various teaching methods and strategies. In addition, the article presents the procedure and the results of the survey conducting.*

Keywords: *precedent phenomena, authentic material, cultural approach, strategy, historical context, survey.*

Introduction.

There is a set of certain "cultural objects" or ideas, which in turn determines and reflects the specifics of national character and linguistic consciousness. This set of objects in the mind of a native speaker of a certain culture is associated with an intensely colored range of feelings or emotions. The appearance of any of these objects in consciousness sets in motion the entire gamut of feelings associated with it. Such subjects are called precedents. To understand the precedent phenomena, let's look at their characteristics discussed in the scientific literature. For example, R. Z. Nazarova and M. V. Zolotareva point out a number of linguistic phenomena that have a precedent character and have the following characteristics: 1) they are well known to all representatives of the national linguistic and cultural community (having a super personal character); 2) they are relevant in cognitive (cognitive and emotional) terms; 3) the appeal to them is constantly renewed in the speech of representatives of one or another national linguistic and cultural community [Nazarova & Zolotareva, 2015].

Understanding precedent phenomena in a globalized world, where effective and meaningful intercultural communication is necessary, is an indispensable skill for any language learner. So, this article is devoted to dealing with ways of successful teaching precedent phenomena in the English language classes at higher schools.

The peculiarities of teaching precedent phenomena.

In the process of learning a foreign language, it is very important to understand the relationship between language and culture. One effective way to overcome this gap is to study precedent phenomena - information of cultural and historical significance embedded in the language. Examples of these are well-known and important phrases, quotes, literary outbursts and historical events.

Teaching English precedent phenomena at the university level not only increases linguistic competence, but also allows students to more deeply assess the cultural context in which the language operates. Authentic English-language texts contain country-specific or culture-marked language units. It is evident, that precedent phenomena provide a vivid linguistic characteristic for representatives of small and large social groups who speak the studied language.

Consequently, precedent phenomena serve as cultural touchstones within a language [Tylohanova & Yankova 2019]. They are deeply rooted in the collective memory of native speakers and often carry meanings far beyond their literal interpretation. For example, phrases like

"Big Brother" from George Orwell's "1984" or Martin Luther King Jr.'s iconic line, "I have a dream," are immediately recognizable to most English speakers and evoke rich associations with surveillance and civil rights, respectively. These references form an integral part of communication, enabling speakers to convey complex ideas succinctly and powerfully.

According to N.K.Shilayeva for educational purposes, it is important to correctly select authentic texts with such phenomena. Examples of precedent texts can be literary works ("The Catcher in the Rye"), jokes, song lyrics, advertisements, proverbs ("Better late than never"), painting titles ("Mona Lisa") or idioms ("Under the weather") [Shilayeva, 2022].

V.L.Latysheva explains that research on any precedent phenomenon remains in the focus of linguistics and psycholinguistics to demonstrate the objective difficulty of describing this phenomenon in an intercultural context [2011]. That is why, teaching the precedent phenomena in English classes at the university requires a combination of linguistic analysis, a cultural approach and the development of practical language skills.

While teaching the functional aspect of precedent phenomena, teachers offer several advantages, such as, *Enhanced Comprehension* where many authentic texts from literature and journals to movies or advertisements rely on precedent phenomena to convey meaning. Language is a reflection of culture, so the study of precedent phenomena greatly helps students to understand the values, history and shared experiences of English-speaking societies. In a practical part of the process mastering precedent phenomena enriches students' ability to participate in comparative-contrast analysis, discussions, write persuasively, and interpret nuanced texts. This skill is invaluable in academic and professional settings.

Teaching precedent phenomena effectively requires a structured and engaging approach. Here are some practical strategies to teach them:

APPROACHES	PROCEDURE	EXAMPLE
Contextual Introduction	Begin by explaining the concept of precedent phenomena and why they matter. Use examples like Shakespearean quotes to illustrate their cultural significance. Discuss how these references are used in modern contexts, such as political speeches or advertisements.	"To be or not to be" "Achilles' heel"
Thematic Exploration	Organize lessons around themes such as literature, politics, or pop culture. Similarly, a lesson on American history could explore phrases.	For instance, a unit on dystopian literature might include discussions of Orwellian terms like " <i>Big Brother</i> " or " <i>doublethink</i> ." like "the Boston Tea Party" or "Manifest Destiny."
Text Analysis	Provide students with authentic materials—such as newspaper articles, movie scripts, or book excerpts—that feature precedent phenomena. Encourage them to analyze how these references contribute to the text's meaning.	For example, students might examine how phrases like "Catch-22" are used to describe paradoxical situations in both literary and everyday contexts.

Interactive Activities	Engage students through group projects, such as researching a famous precedent phenomenon and presenting its origins and contemporary usage. Role-playing or debates incorporating these references can also be effective.	For instance, students could reenact famous historical speeches or write their own using precedent phenomena.
Comparative Analysis	Encourage students to compare precedent phenomena in English with those in their native languages.	For example, explore how different cultures express similar ideas through idioms or proverbs, highlighting both universal themes and unique cultural perspectives.

Teaching precedent phenomena is not without challenges. Students may find it difficult to grasp the cultural nuances or historical context of certain references. To address this, instructors can provide background information first and give simple explanations of complex phenomena. Also, using multimedia resources, such as videos or podcasts can bring references to life. Showing clips from classic films or speeches of famous people can help students see and understand that kind of phenomena in action. Moreover, to make the explanations of precedent phenomena, teachers encourage comparisons with similar phenomena in students' native languages, highlighting universal themes. By offering incremental learning, some instructors start the classes with widely known references and gradually introduce more complex and niche phenomena. In this vein to teach precedent phenomena the most effective activities or exercise by N.K. Shilayeva can be included into instructional input:

- *Read the precedent quotation and write an essay using cultural marked words correctly and paying attention to the linguistic peculiarities of social groups.*
- *Read the socio-cultural situation and make up a dialogue with your partner using socio-cultural aspects accepted in English culture in your speech.*
- *Watch a video about socio-cultural peculiarities of a foreign country, act out the satiations you have watched using precedent phenomena.*
- *Take part in a role-play on the topic, use precedent phenomena in your speech.*

To measure students' progress in understanding and using precedent phenomena, teachers design an appropriate type of assessment. For example, students identify and explain the meaning of various precedent phenomena by taking *quizzes and tests*. *Writing assessments* can help students analyze a text or write an essay incorporating multiple precedent phenomena where *class discussions* create a chance to share their interpretations of precedent phenomena and debate their relevance in modern contexts.

Methodology of research.

Experimental teaching precedent phenomena at English classes was conducted in 2024 at Tashkent State Pedagogical University among the 2-year students on specialty: 70111801 – Foreign languages and literature. There were three stages:

- 1) *preparatory stage* – the initial level of knowledge of students related to English precedent phenomena;
- 2) *the main stage* is experimental learning;

3) *the final stage* is the analysis and generalization of the results of experimental training.

After collecting the first necessary data, an introductory diagnostic survey was conducted before the start of experimental training. When conducting an introductory diagnostic survey, it is important that there are clear indications for the task being performed, that the tasks are purposeful, and that the time of the survey is limited.

The final diagnostic section was carried out in the form of a discussion way. The game assumed the inclusion in its content and in the linguistic equipment of all the language and speech material passed. Before the activity, the students were offered to watch a video. Then students performed a series of exercises:

- matching the precedent phenomena with the context;
- choosing the correct answer to the question;
- finding mistakes and correct them in the precedent text;
- completing the sentences using the precedent phenomena;
- paraphrasing the sentences using the presented precedent phenomena.

The experiment has been conducted among 34 second-year students in two stages: *preparatory and final* and result has shown in Picture 1.

Figure 1. Comparison of indicators of learning the topic at the input and final diagnostic of obtained levels.

The presented indicators of the level of knowledge and skill-usage of precedent phenomena confirm the rationality and efficacy of the described exercises for the 2-year students of pedagogical university.

Conclusion.

Precedent phenomena are keys to uncovering the cultural and historical richness of English language. By incorporating this topic into university-level English classes, teachers contribute significantly to the development of students' linguistic competence and cultural awareness. This not only increases their academic and professional skills, but also contributes to a deeper understanding of the interdependence of language and culture

Through well-organized classes, various sources and activities, and meaningful assessments, teachers can allow students to confidently navigate the complexities of language and culture.

Based on the survey, following results are accomplished:

1) The role and place of precedent phenomena in the development and improvement of students' language proficiency, their use as an effective means of obtaining socio-cultural information expressed through precedent phenomena, is substantiated.

2) The system of exercises for assimilation of precedent phenomena in order to improve the students' communicative competence gives positive results. One group of exercises ensures the assimilation of the precedent phenomena themselves as linguistic units, while the other provides perfect mastery of all components of communicative competence.

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